

D2.1

Improvements and harmonization of the dynamic carbon footprint assessment, tools and database

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

- AGWP - Absolute Global Warming Potential
- APOS - Allocation At The Point Of Substitution
- BC – Black Carbon
- CCI – Climate Change Impact (tool)
- CCS – Carbon Capture and Storage
- DyPLCA - Dynamic Process-based LCA
- ERF - Effective Radiative Forcing

GHG – Greenhouse Gas(es)
GMST – Global Mean Surface Temperature
GMTC – Global Mean Temperature Change
GMTC_{max} – Global Mean Temperature Change Maximum; maximum temperature registered
GMTCd – direct Global Mean Temperature Change
GWP – Global Warming Potential
iGMTC – integrated Global Mean Temperature Change
iGMTC_{LT} – integrated Global Mean Temperature Change at Long-Term
ISIC - International Standard Industrial Classification
IPCC – Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IPCC AR – Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change Assessment Report
IRF – Impulse Response Function
IRFCCF - impulse response function Carbon-Climate Feedback effect on radiative forcing
IRFT - Temperature Impulse Response Function
LCA – Life Cycle Assessment
LCI – Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA – Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LTO – Long-Term effect of methane on Ozone depletion
M – Methane decrease
(NM)VOC – (Non-Methane) Volatile Organic Compounds
OC – Organic Carbon
PMs – Particulate Matter
RCP - Representative Concentration Pathway
RF – Radiative Forcing
RFd - 'direct Radiative Forcing
RF_CCF - Carbon-Climate Feedback Effect on the Radiative Forcing
SLCF - Short-lived climate forcers
STO - Short-Term Ozone increase
SW – Stratospheric Water decrease if the emission is in upper troposphere lower stratosphere
USDA - United States Department of Agriculture
WMGHG – Well-mixed Greenhouse Gas(es)
WTP - Water Treatment Plant

PROJECT INFORMATION

Project full title: Harmonised Life Cycle Assessment methods for sustainable and circular BIO based systems

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List of participants:

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5	NORGES TEKNISK-NATURVITENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET	NTNU
6	BIOECONOMY FOR CHANGE	B4C
7	BUSINESS E-INCUBATOR GO-UP	GOUP
8	FUNDACION CENTRO DE SERVICIOS Y PROMOCION FORESTAL Y DE SU INDUSTRIA DE CASTILLA Y LEON	CESEFOR
9	SONAE ARAUCO PORTUGAL SA	SONAE
10	ASOCIACION PARA LA CERTIFICACION ESPANOLA FORESTAL	PEFC

DELIVERABLE DETAILS

Document Number:	D2.1
Document Title:	Improvements and harmonization of the Dynamic carbon footprint assessment, tools and database
Dissemination level	PU – Public, fully open
Period:	PR1
WP:	WP2 Improved methodologies for environmental sustainability and circularity assessment of bio-based systems (bbs)
Task:	T2.1 Harmonization of existing dynamic carbon footprint methodologies
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Reviewer(s):	Marcos Watanabe (NTNU), Lucia Garcia Santos (CTA)
Abstract:	<p>The climate change impact due to greenhouse gas emissions, mainly CO₂, is a major matter of concern. This is especially the case for biobased products. To assess this, conventionally carbon footprint is applied, meaning here a life cycle assessment focused on climate change effects. Yet, a prominent aspect of these biobased products is the prior uptake of CO₂, its temporary storage before final emission at the end of life. To better cover this aspect, besides other reasons, a dynamic carbon footprint is the way forward. In such an approach, as interpreted here, the differentiation of emissions over time is considered, with related time-differentiated climate change effect. In this context, the aim of this deliverable is to further improve and harmonize this dynamic carbon footprint assessment. Both the inventory and impact assessment phases were improved through four objectives.</p> <p>Regarding the inventory, we focused on adding temporal parameters (emission profile, process duration etc.) to processes, allowing for a temporally differentiated profile.</p> <p>First, LIST finalized this for a complete life cycle inventory database, ecoinvent 3.11 database (~27 000 processes https://ecoinvent.org/), in the form of an updated DyPLCA database, whereas the previous version was a limited one for ecoinvent 3.10. This update was partly automatic but also covered manual adding for ~2000 processes. Such a database allows for a full dynamic carbon footprint, covering the complete background, which remains unseen for any alternative out there.</p> <p>Second, regarding forestry processes, LIST & AAU, added detailed temporal CO₂ profile for the net CO₂ uptake over the full forestry period for ecoinvent processes of prominent EU species, implemented in the DyPLCA database. This was done by</p>

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deriving equations from the Carbon Flux Model output of AAU for datasets that matched theecoinvent species and characteristics (e.g. rotation period).
Coming back on the dynamic climate change impact assessment, this was improved by INSA and implemented in their Climate Change Impact tool (CCI-tool).
As a third objective, they updated this impact with new insights from latest IPCC reports. Concretely, INSA included the indirect effects and the carbon cycle feedback in the characterization.
Fourthly, INSA derived and included the computation for short lived climate forcers, e.g. NOx, based on literature data. This model uses the specific effective radiative forcing (if available; if not, the specific radiative forcing), and the perturbation time (or lifetime).
Finally, INSA illustrated this all through a case study and presented interpretation of dynamic climate change through a harmonized set of metrics.
Overall, the outcomes of this deliverable have advanced the dynamic carbon footprint assessment. Future efforts, that may also be worked out in other deliverables of LCA4BIO, concern particularly prospective characterization (i.e. considering future conditions) and (indirect) land use & land use change effects.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Context

Global concerns about climate change and its impacts induced by greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and processes make it crucial to understand its evolution over time. This is particularly relevant for bio-based systems, which take up CO₂ during biomass growth, of which a part remains stored during the life cycle of products (considering possible recycling, reuse etc.), and there is an eventual release at the final end of life (e.g. via incineration). However, in the field of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and carbon footprint analysis, which focuses on the evaluation of product systems, a static view is still the dominant approach. Dynamic LCA would alter that by starting to consider time-differentiated processes, flows (e.g. GHG) and thus impacts. Few studies have considered dynamic effects, and if so, only by taking into account time differentiation for the foreground system (Beloin-Saint-Pierre et al., 2020). Yet, here are five overall reasons for a dynamic LCA and dynamic carbon footprint specifically:

1. **The extent of the impact can be dependent on the differentiation over time of the stressors** (Pigné et al., 2020). More precisely, the impact of a stressor can be influenced by the profile over time and background conditions. For the former, for example, the toxicity of a compound will largely depend on the dose (amount over time) and not just the amount. This has already been worked out to a certain degree in the dynamic LCA context (Shimako et al., 2017). Regarding background conditions, these evolve over time and so thus may the impact. For example, in the future water extraction may lead to more water scarcity due to more drought in certain regions, as studied in the prospective LCA context (Baustert et al., 2022). Note that this aspect mainly focuses on Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA).
2. **When considering impacts less relevant in future** (Pigné et al., 2020), most notably through discounting or a cut-off. The commonly used Global Warming Potential (GWP) 100 metric integrates the radiation effect of a GHG emission over 100 years and thus already considers a cut-off in radiation effects at year 100 after emission. Variants exist with other time windows, e.g. 20 years or 500 years. Discounting would decrease the value over time through a certain trend, most commonly a percentual decrease per year. In dynamic LCA, such future discounting or cut-off effects can be covered more consistently and holistically by also taking into account the differentiation of the stressors over time itself of a product system. The latter would lead to a beneficial effect of temporal carbon storage in dynamic carbon footprint under such effects. Note that discounting and/or cut-off imply ethical considerations, i.e. considering future impact and generations less relevant, and should be implemented with that in mind (Levasseur et al., 2012).
3. **The transgression of certain boundaries is also dependent on a temporal perspective** (Guinée et al., 2022). For example, certain planetary boundaries such as temperature thresholds, imply a consideration of a temperature profile over time. To that end, there is theoretically a need to consider a time-differentiated assessment of GHG emissions and their contribution to such a temperature profile over time. To evaluate global industry or the share of a product system to transgression, temporal differentiation is needed, implying dynamic LCA.
4. **Permitting for further dynamic considerations that are time dependent.** This chiefly concerns implications at the life cycle inventory (LCI) level, whereas the first reasons focused on the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA). A prominent example of dynamic changes that are time dependent is the alteration of the electricity mix over time, as done in many case studies (Collinge et al., 2013; Negishi et al., 2018). More advanced dynamic effects can be considered, such as market response depending on the timing. Temporal differentiation is a prerequisite for such advancements (Schaubroeck, 2022).
5. **Uptake in standards of dynamic LCA, more precisely dynamic carbon footprint.** Few standards have already explicitly covered consideration of dynamic LCA:
 - a. ISO 14067 GHG – Carbon footprint. In this standard, a dynamic carbon footprint variant is optional.

- b. RE2020 environmental regulation for construction in France. For this standard, the consideration of dynamic carbon footprint is obligatory for the foreground system.

1.2 Aim & objectives

The overall aim of this deliverable is to improve and harmonize the dynamic carbon footprint assessment with four dedicated objectives related with improving existing methods, tools and databases. These can be grouped into objectives concerning the inventory (flows of climate change stressors such as greenhouse gases) and those related to the impact assessment (translation of stressors in climate change impact scores).

Concerning the former, inventory improvement, the following concrete objectives were outlined:

1. addition of temporal parameters (e.g. duration of process) to processes of a recent full background LCA database. This activity by LIST resulted in the creation of an updated Temporal database.
2. Focusing on the forest sector, the implementation of detailed profiles of CO₂ flux over time for the forestry processes in the database, using a dedicated model/tool on this matter from Aalborg University.

Note that no flow amounts were altered, but just a temporal distribution added or superimposed.

For the impact assessment phase, the dynamic climate change impact assessment was to be improved, resulting in a fourth and fifth objective:

3. Update of dynamic characterization modelling for greenhouse gases based on new IPCC reports, with new info & data.
4. Addition of dynamic climate change characterization of short-lived climate change forcers beyond conventional greenhouse gases, e.g. NO_x.

There are some deviations from what is foreseen in the task description of the Grant Agreement as specified below with a justification:

- Pre-calculated datasets of the background database (ecoinvent) are not presented, but are still being run, as part of task 6.2, and will be presented in the associated deliverable. Reasons for this are:
 - a. We are in dialogue with the original life cycle inventory database provider (ecoinvent; <https://ecoinvent.org/>) regarding the possibility to provide normalized temporal profiles for free as was foreseen.
 - b. There are additional complexity and challenges in running the improved software and database due to increasing the database to 27000 processes, the complex forestry processes and the adaptation of the tool from Simapro imports to Brightway.
- There was the notion to possibly develop prospective climate change characterization to cover the altered climate change impact for future climate change stressor emissions. However, as explained in section 3.3.3, current information on this from external sources, notably IPCC, is still lacking at the time of this deliverable. Hence, for this report, we focused on updating dynamic climate change characterization and consideration of the impacts of short-lived compounds. Yet, future research with more adequate data could lead to credible prospective characterization factors and is being explored further by partners in task 3.3.
- Land use change effects are not addressed here as these are instead considered as a focus area for work package 4.

1.3 Report structure

Aligned with the objectives, the report is divided into two sections:

1. Improved life cycle inventory for dynamic carbon footprint (section 2).

2. Improved life cycle impact assessment for dynamic carbon footprint (section 3).

Each section has a separate introduction, specifies background information and State of the art, and finally elaborates on the advancements. We end with an overall conclusion in section 4.

1.4 Annexed files

Besides this report, there are additional annexed deliverable documents:

- For the inventory part, one separate file:
 - Info and datasets of CO₂ uptake functions for ecoinvent forestry datasets based on the Carbon Flux tool of Aalborg (excel file)
- For the impact assessment part, one separate file (excel file) with:
 - Python code for the novel modelling of short-lived climate forcers, implemented in version 2 of the Climate Change Impact tool. This is only the new part of the complete code.
 - Novel parameters and characterization factors for short lived climate forcers. These parameters are explained in the associated report

2 IMPROVED LIFE CYCLE INVENTORY FOR DYNAMIC CARBON FOOTPRINT

2.1 Overview

The life cycle inventory results for the dynamic carbon footprint will cover, differentiated over time, all elementary flows that induce global warming effects. A main category of such flow are greenhouse gases, but section 3 in this report expands this. Coming back on the inventory, this differentiation over time, implies that process duration, process timing, and emission patterns need to be considered. Commonly only the foreground system, i.e. the system of interest, is temporally differentiated in literature (Beloin-Saint-Pierre et al., 2020). Yet, here we build further on a framework that has already been applied to a full background database of temporal parameters, which is explained in the next section, and LIST aimed to improve the framework and its application in two ways:

1. Updating the temporal database
2. Including the temporal profile of net CO₂ flow for forests (with the help of Aalborg University)

Note that in a previous project, CALIMERO, improvements have been made to the DyPLCA tool and database (Schaubroeck et al., 2025), which are specified in the next section.

DISCLAIMER: Throughout this section 2, dynamic only implies temporal differentiation, and not the actual dynamics of processes.

2.1.1 DyPLCA: framework, tool & database

It is only recently that a fully dynamic LCA has been applied (in this case, dynamic only implies temporal differentiation), in particular through the Dynamic Process-based LCA (DyPLCA) framework, tool and related temporal database (Pigné et al., 2020; Tiruta-Barna et al., 2016). At the backbone is a novel modelling approach which we will present first, and then the database and tool are brought forward.

2.1.1.1 *DyPLCA modelling approach*

At the core is a novel (dynamic) LCI modelling approach. It is chiefly elaborated in the work of Tiruta Barna et al. (2016) and further refined by Pigné et al. (2020). We refer to those works for the mathematical equations that form the basis. Here, we just shortly describe the concept behind it and specify key temporal parameters.

The concept entails the iterative tracing of process by process and mapping their temporal profile over time, which emission profiles are superseded into the overall temporal profile of the life cycle. Hereto, the following steps are taken:

1. Retrieving an LCI (matrix);
2. Mapping a graph based on this inventory (matrix);
3. a graph search algorithm is used to travers all these processes considering a predefined combined process & supply model.

Figure 1 below shows how a graph of processes can be represented on the basis of a matrix. When it comes to the process-supply model, this has been uniquely developed by Tiruta-Barna et al. (2016). This model covers a set of equations that first characterize the time profile of processes and their flows using key parameters. Second, considering supply characteristics (e.g. frequency of supply), a combined time profile is generated that considers both temporal characteristics of processes and supply. In Figure 2, a representation is given of the process-supply model and in Table 1; **Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** key parameters are specified. More information can be found in the respective works (Pigné et al., 2020; Tiruta-Barna et al., 2016).

Figure 1. Example of the concept application on an ecoinvent-like process network (Tiruta-Barna et al., 2016, p. 20)

Figure 2. Two subsequent processes: current ecoinvent related data (in red); process model, supply model and their combination. Legend for variables: a_{ij} and b_{kj} : elements of matrix A and B (i, j are processes, k is an environmental intervention); α_{ij} and β_{kij} : production and emission functions for process i ; T : functioning period for the system; t_0 : evaluation's start time; δ : supply delay period; r : production period; τ : period of supply of product 2 for process 1; $\varphi_{2,1}$: supply function from 2 to 1; $\alpha_{2,1}$ and $\beta_{k,2,1}$: production and emission functions for process 2 working for process 1; $g_{k,2,1}$: quantity of k emitted by process 2 when working for process 1 (Tiruta-Barna et al., 2016, p. 20)

Table 1. Temporal parameters considered in the DyPLCA (Dynamic Process-based Life Cycle Assessment) modelling approach.

	Parameter	Name	Significance
Process model (specific for process i)	$\alpha(t)$	Production function	Describes the time shape of the activity (e.g. continuous, constant, discontinuous...)
	$\beta(t)$	Environmental intervention function	Describe the time shape of the emissions/resource consumptions. Usually linked to $\alpha(t)$
	r	Production period	Time between the earliest input (raw material) and the latest output of the activity
	T	Representative period	Life time of the main infrastructure (material support) related to the activity
	t_0	Start date of the analysis	Arbitrary or calendar dependent
Supply model: Continuous or intermittent (process link i-j)	d	Delay	No activity takes place; delay introduced for each delivered batch
	t	Supply period only for intermittent	Interval between 2 consecutive supplies

2.1.1.2 DyPLCA tool

The **modelling approach** has at first hand been translated into an operational program written in the programming language C++, which is commonly faster than Python. It allows to differentiate an inventory over time given an input matrix with the flows between processes and stressors, and a database on temporal parameters.

To more easily apply the DyPLCA model to cases, a more **user-friendly web-based tool** has been developed, available at <http://dypplca.list.lu>. Using this tool, one can add new foreground processes, also fill in temporal parameter data for these and alter temporal parameter data for background processes. Links can be made with background processes, in this case ecoinvent (<https://ecoinvent.org/>) 3.2 processes for which temporal data is available.

See the work of Pigné et al. (2020) for more details.

2.1.1.2.1 Recent improvements in the CALIMERO project

Within the CALIMERO project, in its confidential deliverable D3.4 (Schaubroeck et al., 2025), two main advancements have been made with regard to the DyPLCA model and tool. First, **a new feature, titled bwdypplca, was created to export an LCI modelled in Brightway** to a custom file type that can handle larger matrices. Second, **a new connector** linking the MongoDB database and the calculations performed in the backend was created in Typescript, so DyPLCA could read these bwdypplca files. This was an important step as the ecoinvent matrices have grown by several thousand processes, and the resulting SimaPro export, on which DyPLCA relied, became computationally cumbersome to handle. In time, the SimaPro export function will be re-added as a possible input to the DyPLCA software.

2.1.1.3 DyPLCA database

A DyPLCA database had already been developed that contains data for temporal parameters, as shown in Table

1, for all the processes of ecoinvent 3.2, amounting to about 15 000 processes. Ecoinvent is probably the most commonly and elaborate LCI database applied in the field of LCA (Wernet et al., 2016). No other database exist like DyPLCA at a full background database level, to the best of our knowledge. See an extract in Table 3. This has been done for all three system models of ecoinvent. A very rudimentary classification has been conducted, not based on International Standard Industrial Classification (ISIC) or any other existing classification types, to have values in a more systematic way. However, ecoinvent 3.2 is about 10 years old and thus notably outdated. Therefore, there is a need for a database corresponding to a more recent version of ecoinvent, in this case 3.11.

DISCLAIMER:

The DyPLCA database, older and new versions (incl. the one developed in this deliverable), are confidential. For further information, please contact LIST (thomas.schaubroeck@list.lu).

2.1.1.3.1 CALIMERO Improvements

As part of another project CALIMERO and as explained in its confidential deliverable 3.4 (Schaubroeck et al., 2025), a framework to update the DyPLCA database and an update to ecoinvent 3.10 has largely been performed.

2.1.1.3.1.1 DyPLCA update framework

Two approaches were used to update the database: (1) an automated approach and (2) a manual approach. The sequence described below contains a synopsis of each step; a more in-depth explanation at each level will follow this segment.

Prior to updating the DyPLCA database, an aggregation of the three ecoinvent system models (cut-off by classification, allocation at the point of substitution (APOS) and consequential) into one. More precisely, APOS was considered the default one, so a first list of processes were created that both belonged to the other two. Afterwards, the unique processes of the latter two were added to that list. This was done to match the original DyPLCA database format where such an aggregation had also been performed.

To aid in the big update, a step-wise framework has been worked out.

The **automated approach** is composed of Python scripts to automate a matching of processes between different versions of ecoinvent and to carry over the temporal parameters from the older to newer versions. The onset of this approach comprised several steps. These steps are described in more detail below:

- a. **Naïvely match** to find processes that exist in both ecoinvent versions. Essentially, whenever processes from ecoinvent 3.2 matched exactly in activity name, product name, location, and unit with processes in ecoinvent 3.10, the temporal parameters were copied to these new processes.
- b. **Matching the new geographies** found in ecoinvent 3.10 to those that correspond with geographies or regions in ecoinvent 3.2 (for example, matching Kenyan processes in ecoinvent 3.10 to “Rest of Africa” processes in ecoinvent 3.2). Then the temporal parameters were copied.
- c. Comparing the homogeneity of the temporal data within **matching ISIC classes** and matching ecoinvent 3.2 to ecoinvent 3.10. Thus, if the similarity of the temporal data (regardless of process data) was 90% or more in a given ISIC class in the older version, all processes in the newer version were assigned this value.

Once the limits of a systematic, blanket approach to matching processes was performed, the dataset underwent a **manual matching**. This was performed in two ways:

1. **Proxy-based matching**, where temporal parameters from activities that may be found in other ISIC categories, but are similar in activity or product output, was carried over.

2. **Process-by-process assignment**, where temporal parameters for individual processes were added. This method was most used in the agricultural, forestry, and transport sectors.

2.1.1.3.1.2 Limited DyPLCA database update to ecoinvent 3.10

Using the above approach, DyPLCA was updated to ecoinvent 3.10 to a considerable extent. Certain processes were still left, in particular for the last manual process-by-process step. This is a very time-intensive step and its completion has been continued in this deliverable. See overview in Table 2.

Table 2. Number of processes handled by a certain approach in the update of DyPLCA from ecoinvent 3.2 to ecoinvent 3.10 in the CALIMERO project (Schaubroeck et al., 2025).

	Number of processes addressed	Number of processes left
Before start (ecoinvent 3.10)	0	24 641
Processes without temporality – (actual) market and import processes	5 635	19 006
Automatic approach		
Naïve match	9 672	9 334
Matching on geographies	/ (skipped due to complexity)	/ (skipped due to complexity)
Matching on ISIC classes	2 566	6 768
Manual approach		
Proxy-based	3 630	3 138
Process-by-process	3 138	~1500

Table 3. Illustrative extract of the first DyPLCA (Dynamic Process-based Life Cycle Assessment) database (aligned with ecoinvent 3.2), available as supporting information linked to the work of Pigné et al. (2020)

Spro e32 full name	unit	APOS classification	T (process life span/time) in years	r in days	delta in days	alpha	beta	fixed calendar	tau (days)	continuous supply	market M
1-propanol {RER} production	kg	not mft	50	1	60	1/50	1/50		delta		
Waste mineral oil {CH} treatment of, hazardous waste incineration	kg	mft	30	1	30	1/30	1/30		delta		
Maintenance, barge {RER} processing	unit	not mft	20	1	0	1/20	1/20		365.242		
Machine operation, diesel, >= 74.57, underground mining {GLO} machine operation, diesel, >= 74.57 kW, underground mining	hour	not mft	20	1/24	0	1/20	1/20		r_p	x	
Electricity, high voltage {AT} electricity production, wind, >3MW turbine, onshore	kWh	not mft	25	1/24/60	0	1/25	1/25		r_p	x	
Potato {US} production	kg	not mft	1	365.242	0	$x := t - \text{trunc}(t) ;$ if(x<7/12, 0, if(x<10/12, 4,0))	1	Planting in March to April, harvest in July to September	r_p		
Pulpwood, hardwood, measured as solid wood under bark {RoW} hardwood forestry, beech, sustainable forest management	m3	not mft	140	365.242*140	0	1/140	1/140		r_c		
Cattle for slaughtering, live weight {CA-QC} milk production, from cow	kg	not mft	10	10*365.242	0	1/10	1/10		r_c		
Green bell pepper {GLO} production	kg	not mft	1	365.242/2	0	1	1		r_c		
Transport, freight train {BE} processing	metric ton*km	not mft	40	0.063	0	1/40	1/40		r_c		

2.2 Novel advancements for DyPLCA

2.2.1 Model & tool

During the DyPLCA updates, we updated the MongoDB database to version 7.0; this modernized the infrastructure and now allows for greater flexibility for further developments. Older versions of MongoDB only supported a handful of programming languages (and of those, only certain versions), and the newer versions support additional languages and more versions, allowing for greater flexibility for development.

2.2.2 Update & refinement of DyPLCA database to ecoinvent 3.11

A core task executed by LIST is the update & refinement of the DyPLCA database to ecoinvent 3.11, completing the work that has started in CALIMERO from a limited update to ecoinvent 3.10. The same procedure as in CALIMERO has been applied, described in section 2.1.1.3.1.1 above.

To be able to better backtrack the completion of the database, a column was added with authors names (“AB” for Alya Bolowich & “TS” for Thomas Schaubroeck). AB mainly performed automatic matching and TS manual matching, with a systematic correction afterwards. See respective subsequent section. A comment column has also been added for further comments if need be.

2.2.2.1 Automatic matching

The DyPLCA database underwent a further update to ecoinvent 3.11. Table 4, below, shows how many processes were updated in this automatic way. We can see that updating from one version to the next resulted in a matching of 93% of processes overall (88% naively, 5% with ISIC matching). Because of the geographic specificities of agricultural processes, and the inclusion of the Carbon Flux model for net carbon uptake of different tree species, we removed the agricultural and forestry processes from our matching process in order to handle these manually. This resulted in 187 processes in addition to the 1570 process that needed to be assigned temporal parameters manually (1757 processes in total). The 1109 processes that remained unmatched from ecoinvent 3.10 were ignored, as we only focused on what processes still needed temporal parameters for ecoinvent 3.11. The reasons these ecoinvent 3.10 processes remained unmatched could be due to a host of reasons: no longer existing, change of activity or product name, change in geography, etc.

Table 4. A breakdown of the matching process from ecoinvent 3.10 to ecoinvent 3.11

	Ecoinvent 3.10	Ecoinvent 3.11
# processes to start	24641	26793
unmatched after naïve merge	4381	
...of which	1109	3272
Remaining to match		
after removing markets and imports		2208
after removing agriculture and forestry		2021
after ISIC matching		1570

2.2.2.2 Further Manual completion

There were 1757 processes of ecoinvent 3.11 (+ ~1500 from ecoinvent 3.10) left for manual completion. This was a labour-intensive step. The full description of how this manual completion took place cannot be made due to the confidential nature of the DyPLCA database. The elaboration in this section describes systematic elements but cannot reflect the intensiveness of this effort. Further information for manual completion is specified in the database. Two systematic key strategies have been applied:

- Copied from similar process
- Finding of new temporal data based on ecoinvent description or external references

Due to their complexity and sometimes relevance in the biobased sector, manual addition was preferred for **Agricultural processes**. Their temporal characteristics, notably the moment of harvest and activity (alpha function), are unique due to their seasonality, species-specificity, practice dependency and country-uniqueness. The reasoning behind parameter specification for agricultural production processes has already been presented in Table S7 in the supplementary material of the work of Pigné et al. (2020). Here we shortly repeat these:

After filling in a few agricultural processes, systematic data sources had been unraveled that provided information for many species and countries. These are the following:

- for cereals, crop calendars could be retrieved from the database of the Foreign Agricultural Service of the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) <https://ipad.fas.usda.gov/ogamaps/cropcalendar.aspx>
- Crop calendars were also obtained from the database of the United Nations Food and Agricultural Organization: <https://cropcalendar.apps.fao.org/#/home?id=&crops=0144>
- Harvest calendars, especially for fruits, obtained from Tridge Intelligence and data (typing in “harvest calendar” for a certain species), <https://medium.com/tridge/lentil-harvest-calendar-by-variety-35ac853d380c>

Note that these sources are not always complete and may not fully align, e.g. for millet production in India there is a difference between the sources from Tridge and USDA.

Yet, there are also many agricultural processes for which temporal parameters were copied from those that already had, e.g. for countries from the same region.

For the forestry sector, we improved the emission profile of carbon dioxide by coupling with Aalborg University’s Carbon Flux Model (De Rosa et al., 2017; Lancz et al., 2024). This is explained in section 2.2.3.

2.2.2.3 Correction step: Exceptional cases

There are many special cases, beyond sectors, that should be addressed fittingly. Many such special cases have already been described and considered in the work of Pigné et al. (2020) for the temporal database for ecoinvent 3.2. Yet, now, new processes and special cases may present themselves and in the automatic update procedure where sector data is considered the same for all processes belonging to it, as applied for the update from ecoinvent 3.2 to 3.11, these have been sometimes overturned. To correct for this, a consistent re-analysis and re-adaptation had to be executed. In other words, a correction step had to be executed. Here we give an overview of these special cases, and the conducted corrections. **The first set of special cases cover processes that are not actual processes (transformation or transportation)**, and are thus assigned no temporal values, i.e. happening instantaneously.

Market processes in ecoinvent cover primarily a mix of alternatives, possibly with representative transportation and leakage/losses considered. Commonly they are called “market for” processes. These processes are not actual transformation or transportation process and should therefore not have any temporal parameters assigned to them, i.e. it is presumed that they happen instantaneously. Yet, there are some exceptions:

- *Market for high/low/medium voltage electricity*: these cover the actual transportation of electricity without linking to any separate transportation processes. Hence this was considered a very fast transportation process with temporal parameters.
- *Market for natural gas, low pressure*: these cover the actual transportation of natural gas, without linking to any separate transportation processes. Hence this was considered a very fast transportation process with temporal parameters.

Note that for market processes for other fossil fuels, transportation emissions or losses are considered. Yet, there are linkages to separate transportation activities which already take up time. Hence, to not double count time, these are considered as instantaneous market processes. Note that this is a deviation for certain fossil fuels from the work of Pigné et al. (2020). In the correction step, we especially had to correct the exceptions, being the market for electricity and those of fossil fuels.

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Linkage/renaming processes in ecoinvent entail the linkage with other activities. These are also no real transformation or transportation processes. An overview of some of these are processes with labels:

- *to generic market*, which link to general market
- *to market for*, which cover the linkage to a certain market
- *import from*, which cover the import of certain goods to other market
 - a. with exception of “evaporation of natural gas, import from” which is covers the evaporation of liquid to gas

In the correction step, we changed these all to instantaneous, regardless of what was coming out of the systematic update.

Finally, there are **empty processes** in ecoinvent that cover no linkage at all. These are notably waste stream processes with “recycled content”, coming from the cut-off model of ecoinvent where waste streams are considered burden-free and no processes are linked. They are then used in possible waste valorization processes. An exception is: “paper production, woodfree, uncoated, “x%” recycled content, at non-integrated mill”, since this is a production process based on paper waste. In the correction step, we changed these all to instantaneous, regardless of what was coming out of the systematic update.

The second set of special processes that we paid attention to the in the correction step are **services**. Services are product flows that are consumed during or after the consuming processes. Most notably, the treatment of waste are services that do not happen before a consuming process as waste is generated during or after it. These waste treatment processes are registered as negative input flows, as they are output flows. All processes with negative flows as reference flows were characterized and treated as services.

2.2.3 Improvement of temporal profile forest carbon fluxes

In this section we describe the approach of deriving and implementing the net CO₂ flux of forest ecosystems in DyPLCA for ecoinvent 3.11 forestry processes using the Carbon flux Model/Tool of the University of Aalborg. Results and data are presented in a separate excel file, annexed to this deliverable.

2.2.3.1 *Explanation on University Aalborg's Carbon Flux tool*

The Carbon Flux Model, developed by De Rosa et al. (2017), is a dynamic forest carbon modelling tool, developed by Aalborg University. It provides time-explicit accounts of biomass growth, removals and decay, carbon uptake, and carbon emissions in a forest plot under a user-defined time horizon. The tool has the flexibility to model different plantations, harvesting operations, and functions of biomass growth and decay.

The results of the Carbon Flux Model include a yearly account of cumulative net carbon uptake in the forest plot. There are further characteristics of the tool but they are not of relevance in the context of this LCA4BIO deliverable report. The most important input parameters include rotation time, mean annual increment of biomass, basic wood density, carbon content of the dry mass, the conversion ratio between total and merchantable biomass, and the harvested ratios of the different carbon pools.

In its original release the tool has been applied to a specific case study of a Swedish spruce plantation but have been since updated by Aalborg University under the ALIGNED project to include input data for other species at different locations as well. In the latter project, sensitivity analysis and validation of the modelling results of several different species, were also carried out. The tool, incl. its database, is freely available and can be found in the online repository of the ALIGEND project (Lancz et al., 2024).

2.2.3.2 *Matching & specification of forest carbon flux datasets with ecoinvent forestry processes*

The Carbon Flux Tool (De Rosa et al., 2017; Lancz et al., 2024) contains a managed forest database providing values for the model input parameters for over 240 species and geographical locations. In this subtask, AAU expanded the managed forest database to include several of the most prominent species modelled in the

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ecoinvent 3.11 (<https://ecoinvent.org/>) database. For the following selected species in ecoinvent– birch, spruce and pine in Sweden, oak, spruce, pine and beech in Germany, azobe in Cameroon, and paraná pine in Brazil – datapoints for the required model input parameters were extracted from their respective ecoinvent dataset documentation. This data covers over 60% of the forestry datasets in ecoinvent.

Where the ecoinvent documentation was incomplete or lacking resolution, data previously collected for the compilation of the managed forest database was used. Values for rotation time, mean annual increment and basic wood density were always matched to ecoinvent process information whenever possible, while for parameters like the carbon content of the wood, the biomass conversion and expansion factors and the ratio of below-ground and above-ground biomass, more species- and location-specific values from the existing database were preferred. The source used is specified for each datapoint in the managed forest database and the Carbon Flux Model. See the separate excel file, where an overview is presented of the matching, input data & yearly carbon flux outcome. An example of a net carbon uptake profile by a Beech stand in Germany is presented in the below Figure 3.

Figure 3. Net carbon uptake by a beech forestry stand (Germany), adapted for ecoinvent 3.11, obtained from running the Forest Carbon Flux model. This figure serves as an example.

Some species available in ecoinvent 3.11 remain unmatched at this stage, due to data limitations or, in the case of mixed forests, the incompatibility with the current version of the Carbon Flux Model.

Finally, results of the Carbon Flux model are cumulative yearly flow amounts, which were transformed to non-cumulative yearly ones by considering the differences per year.

2.2.3.3 Adaptation of forest carbon fluxes to DyPLCA

LIST derived from the emission amounts of the Aalborg tool that forest management processes in the tool account for three main mechanisms, for which carbon fluxes should be properly represented in the DyPLCA model

1. the main growth process is represented by a normal distribution
2. Net carbon uptake is higher during the first year of growth
3. thinnings occur at various times (2 or 3 occurrences) during the lifetime of a tree.

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For the first mechanism, the normal distribution is modelled as a Gaussian function with three parameters (a , b , and c), such that:

$$\beta(t) = ae^{-\frac{(t-b)^2}{2c^2}}$$

Parameters a , b , and c are calculated by fitting to the originally calculated carbon flux profiles, ignoring the first year and thinnings. In addition, for the other two mechanisms, the first year uptake and thinnings are added to the equation using “if” statements, with a condition on time t . Moreover, by definition, the emission profile (beta function) should always sum up to 1, hence normalization is required. This is done by calculating the sum of emissions S between $t = 0$ and $t = T$, and dividing the emission profile by S . Formally, S is defined as

$$S = \int_0^T ae^{-\frac{(t-b)^2}{2c^2}} dt + cu_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n th_i = ac \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \left[\operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{T-b}{c\sqrt{2}}\right) - \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{-b}{c\sqrt{2}}\right) \right] + cu_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n th_i$$

with erf the Gauss error function, cu_0 the initial carbon uptake, and th_i the carbon emission due to thinning i , for n thinnings in total. As an example, this is the equation for the net carbon dioxide uptake of process “hardwood forestry, beech, sustainable forest management, “ in Germany (DE), in terms that can be directly parsed by DyPLCA as a function of t :

$6.71 / 310.76 * \exp(-((t-70.50)^2) / (2*24.19^2))$ $+ \operatorname{if}(t < 1, 4.35, 0)$ $+ \operatorname{if}(t < 35.0, 0, \operatorname{if}(t < 36.0, -12.01, 0))$ $+ \operatorname{if}(t < 70.0, 0, \operatorname{if}(t < 71.0, -45.68, 0))$ $+ \operatorname{if}(t < 105.0, 0, \operatorname{if}(t < 106.0, -41.54, 0))$	-1 , a , b , c , S , for Gaussian function initial carbon uptake in the first year carbon emission on first thinning carbon emission on second thinning carbon emission on third thinning
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Implicit assumptions made are:

1. Initial carbon uptake is continuous during the entire first year of forest growth.
2. Thinning episodes lead to carbon emissions that are continuous during the entire year when thinning occurs.

In reality, these processes are most likely seasonal, or in any case shorter than a calendar year. See the separate excel file, where an overview is presented of derived equations.

These profiles are specifically valid for the ecoinvent elementary flow “carbon dioxide, in air” as a resource, which should represent the net carbon dioxide uptake. The flow amount itself of ecoinvent is not altered, which is also the case for DyPLCA as a whole, and this function just imposes a temporal profile on these. Since DyPLCA is limited in covering only one beta function per profile, this profile is thus also superimposed on other elementary flows. Yet, we focus and stick to carbon footprint where these other elementary flows (mainly land use) have commonly no role to play. If one covers indirect land use change effects driven by land use elementary flows (Schmidt et al., 2015), there could be a coverage of these in carbon footprint. Hence, then the profile would then need to be corrected.

Finally, the consideration of this elementary flow for net carbon uptake as a negative flow (-1) is part of the impact assessment method.

2.3 References

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3 IMPROVED LIFE CYCLE IMPACT ASSESSMENT FOR DYNAMIC CARBON FOOTPRINT

3.1 Introduction

We focus on a method to evaluate the climate change impact in dynamic LCA based on a time-dependent model. The static Global Warming Potential (GWP) metric has significant limitations especially when dealing with biogenic carbon emissions and capture processes, and when the time horizon of the evaluation is shorter than 100 years, which is the case of the present and future years and of our whole century. Criticism of the GWP metrics have been expressed from the outset of its use, but, the complexity of climate models has hampered the use of more relevant metrics. However, the reduced models released by climatologists allow the use of alternative climate indicators, closer to physical parameters and with more consistent meaning, like time dependent radiative forcing or time dependent temperature change. More development on this discussion in the realm of dynamic LCA is available elsewhere (Tiruta-Barna, 2021).

A tool (CCI-tool) was previously developed to calculate global climate parameters, i.e. radiative forcing and global mean temperature change and applied with dynamic LCA (Shimako et al., 2016). In the context of LCA4BIO, this tool was improved and completed with the most recent developments in the field (presented in IPCC AR5 and AR6, and related bibliography), as explained in this report. Concretely, two advancements were made:

- Update of model and data for dynamic climate change impact characterization in general
- Addition of dynamic impact characterization for short lived climate forcers, different from greenhouse gases

A case study is also presented to illustrate the implication of a dynamic carbon footprint versus a conventional one, considering the advancements made in characterization modelling. A harmonized overview of dynamic climate change metrics is also presented and how to interpret them.

The new code and model parameters for climate change stressors is presented as additional separate file annexed to this report.

3.2 The principles of the climate change impact (CCI) model

The model is based on the IPCC bibliography and uses the impulse response function (IRF) approach to calculate the radiative forcing (RF) and the global mean temperature change (GMTC).

The atmospheric burden of substance s , B_s , is calculated as the convolution product (symbol $*$) between the temporal emissions of the substance s , g_s ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$) and the concentration – impulse response function of that substance, IRF_s :

$$B_s(t) = g_s * \text{IRF}_s = \int_0^t g_s(t') \text{IRF}_s(t - t') dt' \quad (1)$$

The RF is calculated as the product between the radiative efficiency, A_s , and the atmospheric burden, B_s . The radiative efficiency A_s ($\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) can be considered as time-invariant for small emissions. In the followings, the convolution symbol will be used for simplicity and clarity. We call the RF of direct GHG ‘direct RF’ RFd_s :

$$\text{RFd}_s(t) = A_s(t) B_s(t) = A_s(t)(g_s * \text{IRF}_s) \quad (1)$$

The global mean temperature change generated by the forcer s is defined as the convolution product between its radiative forcing and the temperature impulse response function (IRFT). For direct GHG substances, we call this parameter ‘direct GMTC’ GMTCd_s :

$$\text{GMTCd}_s(t) = \text{RFd}_s * \text{IRFT} \quad (3)$$

IRFT(t) is defined by:

$$\text{IRFT}(t) = \sum_{j=1}^2 \frac{c_j}{a_j} e^{-t/a_j} \quad (4)$$

with the parameter values updated in AR6 WG1 (ch 6SM). IRFT is independent of the type of GHG. However, it may be different if for specific forcers IRFT is determined by specific pathways, e.g. not including a “burden – RF – GMTC” modelling pathway.

3.2.1 Developments performed in the framework of LCA4BIO.

In AR5 Ch 8, 8.7.1.4. it is recommended to include the indirect effects and the carbon cycle feedback in the characterization of the considered compound. For example, for CH₄, include direct effect, indirect effects (oxidation to water) and the neo-formed CO₂ effect, plus the carbon cycle feedback. According to the IPCC AR6 report, the carbon-climate feedback effect on the radiative forcing, RF_{CCF}, is added to the direct radiative forcing (and the other cascade indicators), for all climate forcers (except CO₂) as follows:

$$RF_CCF_s(t) = A_{CO_2}(GMTCd_s * IRFCCF * IRF_{CO_2}) \quad (5)$$

$$RF_s(t) = RFd_s(t) + RF_CCF_s(t) \quad (6)$$

RF_{CCF_s}(t) is the contribution of substances to the supplementary RF of CO₂ due to the temperature elevation generated by s. It is accounted for s together with the RF generated directly by s.

The same holds for the temperature:

$$GMTC_CCF_s(t) = RF_CCF_s * IRFT \quad (7)$$

$$GMTC_s(t) = GMTCd_s + GMTC_CCF_s \quad (8)$$

Where IRFCCF is the impulse response function (CO₂ flux perturbation following a unit temperature pulse), in kg CO₂ yr⁻¹ K⁻¹.

$$IRFCCF(t) = \gamma \delta(t) - \gamma \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{\alpha_i}{\tau_i} e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_i}} \quad (9)$$

See Gasser et al, 2017; and IPCC AR6, 7.SM.5.

The dynamic global RF (W.m⁻²) for all climate forcers taken together is then:

$$RF(t) = \sum_s RF_s(t) \quad (10)$$

Cumulated radiative forcing, iRF (W.m⁻².year), over a given time span TH is:

$$iRF(TH) = \int_{t=t_0}^{TH} RF(t)dt \quad (11)$$

The global mean temperature change at a given time t, GMTC (K), is obtained by aggregating values for all the concerned forcers:

$$GMTC(t) = \sum_s GMTC_s(t) \quad (12)$$

Cumulated temperature change, iGMTC (K.year), is calculated as:

$$iGMTC(TH) = \int_{t=t_0}^{TH} GMTC(t)dt \quad (13)$$

3.3 Specific IRFs for the climate forcers implemented in CCI-tool

3.3.1 Well-mixed GHG (WMGHG)

CO₂

$$IRF(t) = a_0 + a_1 e^{-t/\tau_1} + a_2 e^{-t/\tau_2} + a_3 e^{-t/\tau_3} \text{ and } \sum_i a_i = 1 \quad (1)$$

Methane CH₄

$$IRF(t) = (1 + f_1 + f_2)e^{-t/\tau} \quad (2)$$

where f_1 (0.5) and f_2 (0.15) (IPCC AR5 8.SM.11.3.2) are corrections due to effects on ozone and stratospheric water, respectively.

Methane is oxidized to CO_2 , which is included in the model. The yield of transformation is 75%, i.e. 1 kg of CH_4 generates 2.1 ± 0.7 kg CO_2 as specified in AR6 ch 7.

Dinitrogen oxide (or nitrous oxide) N_2O

$$IRF(t) = \left(1 - 0.36 (1 + f_1 + f_2) \frac{A_{CH_4}}{A_{N_2O}}\right) e^{-t/\tau} \quad (3)$$

With f_1 and f_2 as in eq (2).

Other WMGHG

$$IRF(t) = e^{-t/\tau} \quad (4)$$

The constants used for all GHGs are taken from the last updates (IPCC AR5 and AR6). All the GHGs present in ecoinvent 3.9 LCA data base are included in the software.

3.3.2 Short-lived climate forcers SLCF

The IPCC AR5 ch 8.7.2.4. reveals large differences in emission metrics from air, land and sea emissions, for the SLCF compounds. In the following, the data used according to the emission compartment is mentioned.

The implemented model uses the specific effective radiative forcing (if available; if not, the specific radiative forcing), and the perturbation time (or lifetime) of the SLCFs. The regionality of the SLCF cannot be included in the modeling for the moment because of lack of regional values for the model parameters. In this work, the updated values of ERF per unit emission from Lee et al (2021) for aviation emissions. Data were completed for all the other SLCFs and for all lifetime values from Fuglestedt et al (2010). Data from Lee et al. (2021) are evaluated based on the ERF (effective radiative forcing – evaluated at the TOA top of the atmosphere) while the more ancient data from Fuglestedt et al (2010) are based on RF.

Nitrogen oxides No_x

The indirect climate contribution is due to four effects: the short-term ozone increase (STO), long-term effect of methane on ozone depletion (LTO), methane decrease (M), and stratospheric water decrease if the emission is in upper troposphere lower stratosphere (SW). Each of the components have a specific perturbation time τ . For a pulse unitary emission of No_x , 1 kg N:

$$RF_{No_x} = STO + LTO + M + SW = A_{No_x} IRF(t)$$

$$RF_{No_x}(t) = A_{STO} e^{-t/\tau_1} + A_{LTO} e^{-t/\tau_2} + A_M e^{-t/\tau_3} + A_{SW} e^{-t/\tau_4} \quad (1)$$

$$RF_{No_x}(t) = A_{STO} e^{-t/\tau_1} + (A_{LTO} + A_M + A_{SW}) e^{-t/\tau_2} \quad (2)$$

For aviation emissions in high troposphere – low stratosphere, the data from Lee et al (2021) were used. For shipping emissions (surface of the sea), the data from Fuglestedt et al (2010) were used. For all other compartments of emissions, data from Fuglestedt et al (2010) were used.

Remark

Only for practical utilisation in CCI-tool, the formula can be re-written as:

$$RF_{No_x}(t) = A_{No_x}(a_0 + a_1 e^{-t/\tau_1} + a_2 e^{-t/\tau_2} + a_3 e^{-t/\tau_3}) \quad (1')$$

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With $a_0 = 0$, $A_{\text{Nox}} a_1 = A_{\text{STO}}$ with short τ_1 ; $A_{\text{Nox}} a_2 = A_{\text{LTO}} + A_{\text{M}} + A_{\text{SW}}$ with the same τ_2 ; and $a_3=0$.

LTO, M and SW have the same perturbation time τ_2 which is those of methane lifetime in the given conditions, so the three components can be aggregated in one e-fold term e^{-t/τ_2} .

Carbon monoxide CO

Same modelling approach as in the case of Nox. Three components are included in the indirect effect of CO: short-term ozone increase (STO), long-term effect of methane on ozone depletion (LTO) and methane decrease (M). Only tropospheric (surface) emissions are considered (from Fuglestvedt et al., (2010)). For the unitary emission of 1 kg CO:

$$\text{RF}_{\text{CO}}(t) = A_{\text{STO}} e^{-t/\tau_1} + (A_{\text{LTO}} + A_{\text{M}})e^{-t/\tau_2} \quad (3)$$

Volatile organic compounds others than methane (VOC or NMVOC)

The same approach and formulation as in (3), for 1 kg VOC emitted to surface air. The composition of VOC and the specific parameters are given in Fuglestvedt et al (2010).

Stratospheric water

In case of aviation emissions of water, the radiative forcing increases:

$$\text{RF}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}(t) = A_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} e^{-t/\tau_1} \quad (4)$$

Hydrogen H₂

Hydrogen has an indirect climate effect due to interaction with OH radicals. The radiative forcing of a 1kg H₂ emission is taken from Hauglustaine et al (2022):

$$\text{RF}_{\text{H}_2}(t) = A_{\text{H}_2} e^{-t/\tau_1} \quad (5)$$

Aerosols: Sulfate or sulfur dioxide SO₂; black carbon C; organic carbon C.

The direct effect of aerosols is considered (radiation reflection) in one e-fold term as:

$$\text{RF}_{\text{aerosol}}(t) = A_{\text{aerosol}} e^{-t/\tau_1} \quad (6)$$

For aviation emissions, data from Lee et al (2021) are considered.

For other emission compartments, data from Fuglestvedt et al (2010) are used.

For shipping SO₂, the indirect effect of modification of cloud properties and of the albedo from Lauer et al (2007) is included; for 1 kg SO₂ emission:

$$\text{RF}_{\text{SO}_2/\text{sulphate}}(t) = (A_{\text{direct}} + A_{\text{indirect}}) e^{-t/\tau_1} \quad (7)$$

In case of black carbon the base is kg carbon. For organic carbon, the parameters are also expressed per carbon, considering a ratio “particulate organic matter”/“organic carbon” = 1.4

Other aerosols : particulate matter

Most Particulate Matter (PMs) are generated by combustion processes and are composed in majority by organic compounds (e.g. Perrone et al. 2013). We use the data from Fuglestvedt et al (2010) for “organic

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carbon” to model the behaviour of PMs. Equation (6) applies for particulate matter like PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀.

Since we don't have models for mineral aerosols effect, only the organic part of the particulate matter is included. The composition from Perrone et al (2013) is considered here, i.e. 17 – 24% (w/w) of organic carbon, with no distinctions according to sites or seasons. With the average value of 20.5%, we obtain for the mass of carbon in PMs and for the radiative efficiency of PMs:

$$C = 0.205 \cdot PM \text{ (kg)} \quad \text{and} \quad A_{PM} = 0.205 \cdot A_C \quad (8)$$

The CCI-tool covers PMs in “Data files” with the following notation: “Particulates, 2.5 um”; “Particulates, 10 um”; “Particulates, 2.5 um-10 um”. These notations are used in the template file; they are not exactly the same as in ecoinvent because of the incompatibility with programming rules (names of files can not contain special characters like > <, for instance). In the Data file, the radiative efficiency is A_C (those of organic carbon) but the correction factor 0.205 is applied.

Contrails and induced cirrus (aviation)

The model from Lee et al (2021) is considered on the base of 1 km hole flight:

$$RF_{\text{contrail cirrus}}(t) = A_{\text{contrail cirrus}} e^{-t/\tau_1} \quad \text{with } A \text{ in } (W \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ km}^{-1}) \quad (9)$$

3.3.3 Challenges for Prospective characterization

A literature survey was performed to address the prospective aspect in dynamic climate change indicators, i.e. the effect of the Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP) scenarios considering future conditions, which would influence the characterization of future climate change stressor emissions, potentially translated into prospective characterization factors. The influence of the GHG concentrations in the atmosphere and of the temperature change on the climate emission metrics AGWP/GWP was studied in several papers. Several phenomena intervene in the CO₂ radiative forcing behaviour: the radiative efficiency A_{CO_2} which decreases when the concentration increases, and the CO₂ distribution between compartments which depends on the concentrations. Then the climate carbon cycle feedback acts as a response to the temperature increase.

Reisinger et al (2011) found that “the AGWP of CO₂ decreases under all RCPs, although for longer time horizons this decrease is smaller than for short time horizons due to increased climate–carbon cycle feedbacks.” For methane and N₂O, the effect is also about 10% to 30% depending on the RCP. The authors mention that “the declining radiative efficiency is more than counterbalanced by the increasing fraction of a CO₂ pulse emission that remains in the atmosphere, due to particularly strong climate–carbon cycle feedbacks in this model. “Under the RCP3-PD, which is consistent with a best-estimate global average temperature increase of somewhat less than 2°C over preindustrial conditions, the 100-year AGWP of CO₂ would decrease by only about 2% by 2100 relative to the year 2000 value. By contrast, under the highest RCP8.5, the CO₂ 100-year AGWPs would decrease by 36% by 2100.”

From the three elements competing in the CO₂ global effect, i.e. its radiative efficiency, redistribution between environmental compartments and climate -carbon cycle feedback, the redistribution cannot be implemented (at least at the present time) because the necessary IRF functions (e.g. formula (1) in case of CO₂) are not available for different concentration-temperature conditions (different RCPs).

In this sense, the approach of Lan and Yao (2022) cannot be validated. Indeed, in their publication, the authors used only the radiative efficiency variation, without any other parameter related to the environmental fate of the GHGs. Their results underestimate the effect of CO₂ for instance, for the different RCPs.

Hence, we restrained for this deliverable to derive prospective characterization due to contemporary lacking consensual and credible data and information with regard to future conditions and effects.

3.4 Data used with the model

Data were updated following the information available at present, especially from the IPCC AR6 report completing the AR5 (in which more detailed data are presented).

For IRFT(t) – formula (4), updated data in AR6 WG1 ch 6.SM are used:

$$d1 = 3.4 \text{ years} \quad c1 = 0.44 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C W}^{-1} \text{ m}^2$$

$$d2 = 285 \text{ years} \quad c2 = 0.32 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C W}^{-1} \text{ m}^2$$

All data are implemented in the “Data files” for use with CCI-tool. Concerning the SLCFs, the tables below indicate the main modelling features and present the data selected from bibliography according to the recommendations from the IPCC reports.

Table 5. Information extracted from AR6, ch 6 (table 6.1).

Table 6.1 | Overview of SLCFs of interest for Chapter 6. For each SLCF, its source types, lifetime in the atmosphere, and associated radiatively active agent is given. Source type can be primary (emitted) and/or secondary (formed through multiple atmospheric mechanisms). Unless otherwise noted, the stated lifetime refers to tropospheric lifetime.* Climate effect of increased SLCFs is indicated as ‘+’ for warming and ‘-’ for cooling. ‘Direct’ is used for SLCFs exerting climate effects through their radiative forcing and ‘Indirect’ for SLCFs which are precursors affecting the atmospheric burden of other climatically active compounds. Other processes through which SLCFs affect climate are listed where applicable. The World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines for air quality (AQ) are given, where applicable, to show which SLCFs are regulated for air-quality purposes.

Compounds	Source Type	Lifetime	Direct	Indirect	Climate Forcing	Other Effects on Climate ^a	WHO AQ Guidelines ^b
CH ₄	Primary	~9 years ~12 years (perturbation time)	CH ₄	O ₃ , H ₂ O, CO ₂	+		No ^c
O ₃	Secondary	Hours to weeks	O ₃	CH ₄ , secondary organic and sulphate aerosols	+	Ecosystems	100 µg m ⁻³ 8-hour mean
NO _x (= NO + NO ₂)	Primary	Hours to days		O ₃ , nitrate aerosols, CH ₄	+/-	Ecosystems	40 µg m ⁻³ annual mean 200 µg m ⁻³ 1-hour mean
CO	Primary + Secondary	1 to 4 months		O ₃ , CH ₄	+		No
NMVOCs**	Primary + Secondary	Hours to months		O ₃ , CH ₄ , organic aerosols	+/-		No
SO ₂	Primary	Days (trop.) to weeks (strat.)		Sulphate and nitrate aerosols, O ₃	-	Ecosystems	20 µg m ⁻³ 24-hour mean 500 µg m ⁻³ 10-minute mean
NH ₃	Primary	Hours		Ammonium Sulphate, Ammonium Nitrate	-	Ecosystems	No
HCFCs	Primary	Months to years	HCFCs	O ₃	+/-		No ^c
HFCs	Primary	Days to years	HFCs		+		No ^c
Halons and Methylbromide	Primary	Years	Halons and Methylbromide	Stratospheric O ₃	+/-		No ^c
Very Short-lived Halogenated Species (VSLs)	Primary	Less than 6 months		O ₃	-		No ^c
Sulphate aerosols	Secondary	Minutes to weeks	Sulphate		-	Clouds Ecosystems	as part of PM ^d
Nitrate aerosols	Secondary	Minutes to weeks	Nitrate		-	Clouds Ecosystems	as part of PM ^d
Carbonaceous Aerosols	Primary + Secondary	Minutes to Weeks	BC, OA		+/-	Cryo, Clouds Ecosystems	as part of PM ^d
Sea spray	Primary	Day to week	Sea spray		-	Clouds Ecosystems	as part of PM ^d
Mineral dust	Primary	Minutes to Weeks	Mineral dust		+/-	Cryo Cloud Ecosystems	as part of PM ^d

* For lifetimes reported in this table, it is assumed that the compounds are uniformly mixed throughout the troposphere, however, this assumption is unlikely for compounds with lifetimes <1 year and, therefore, the reported values should be viewed as approximations (Prather et al., 2001).

** Some NMVOCs are biogenic volatile organic compounds (BVOCs).

^a Clouds: effect on clouds through aerosol–cloud interactions, Ecosystems: effect on ecosystems through changes in radiation and deposition, Cryo: effect on planetary albedo through deposition on snow and ice;^b Krzyzanowski and Cohen (2008); ^c regulated through Kyoto/Montreal protocols; ^d For Particulate Matter with diameter <2.5 µm (PM_{2.5}): 10 µg m⁻³ annual mean or 25 µg m⁻³ 24-hour mean (99th percentile) and for Particulate Matter with diameter <10 µm (PM₁₀): 20 µg m⁻³ annual mean or 50 µg m⁻³ 24-hour mean (99th percentile).

Table 6. Specific SLCF emissions in air sub-compartments in ecoinvent, relevant literature and literature recommended by IPCC AR5 (WG1, ch 8).

Compartments	Elementary flows in ecoinvent	Specific from literature	Cited in IPCC AR5, WG1, ch8 (2013)
Air/lower stratosphere + upper troposphere	e.g. From aviation All gases	Nox , Water, Contrails, AIC (Fuglestvedt et al 2010) Nox, Soot (BC), Sulphate, Water, Contrail cirrus (Lee et al, 2021)	Nox (Fuglestvedt et al 2010 ; Kohler et al 2013 ; Myhre et al 2011)
All others air/sub-compartments	All gases	CO (Fuglestvedt et al 2010) VOC (Fuglestvedt et al 2010) BC (Fuglestvedt et al 2010) OC (Fuglestvedt et al 2010) SO ₂ -aerosols (Fuglestvedt et al 2010) H ₂ (Hauglustain et al 2022)	CO (Fuglestvedt et al 2010) CO (Shindell et al 2009) VOC (Fuglestvedt et al 2010) BC (Fuglestvedt et al 2010) BC (Bond et al, 2013, 2011) OC (Bond et al 2011) OC (Fuglestvedt et al 2010)
NEW air/sub-compartments	Not existent in ecoinvent		
Emission from the surface – land		Nox (Fuglestvedt et al 2010)	Nox (Fuglestvedt et al 2010) Nox (Shindell et al 2009) Nox (Shindell et Faluvegi, 2010) SO ₂ (Shindell et Faluvegi, 2010) BC (Bond et al, 2011) OC (Bond et al, 2011)
Emission from shipping (surface-sea)		Nox (Fuglestvedt et al 2010) SO ₂ -aerosols (Fuglestvedt et al 2010)	Nox (Fuglestvedt et al 2010) Nox (Collins et al 2010) SO ₂ (Fuglestvedt et al 2010)

Table 7. Parameter values for SLCFs used in this work.

Air sub-compartment Climate forcer	Forcing parameter	Perturbation time (or lifetime or adjustment time) (years)	Specific forcing A ($W m^{-2} kg^{-1}$)	Name used in ecoinvent
Air/all compartments Except for aviation and shipping	Radiative forcing	Lifetime (years)	Specific forcing ($W m^{-2} kg^{-1}$) used in this work	
NOx :	$W m^{-2} kg_N^{-1} y$ Fuglestedt et al (2010) citing Wild et al (2001)	Fuglestedt et al (2010)	$W m^{-2} kg_N^{-1}$	Nitrogen oxides
Short-term O ₃ increase	$4.59 \cdot 10^{-12}$	0.267	$1.720 \cdot 10^{-11}$	
Long-term O ₃ decrease	$-1.79 \cdot 10^{-12}$	14.2	$-1.261 \cdot 10^{-13}$	
CH ₄ decrease	$-3.80 \cdot 10^{-12}$	14.2	$-2.676 \cdot 10^{-13}$	
CO :	$W m^{-2} kg_{CO}^{-1} y$ Fuglestedt et al (2010) citing Derwent et al 2001		$W m^{-2} kg_{CO}^{-1}$	Carbon monoxide
Short-term O ₃ increase	$6.00 \cdot 10^{-14}$	0.267	$2.247 \cdot 10^{-13}$	
Long-term O ₃ decrease	-	-	-	
CH ₄ decrease	$1.30 \cdot 10^{-13}$	14.2	$1.057 \cdot 10^{-14}$	
VOC :	$W m^{-2} kg_{VOC}^{-1} y$ Fuglestedt et al (2010) citing Collins et al (2002)		$W m^{-2} kg_{VOC}^{-1}$	NMVOC, non-methane volatile organic compounds, unspecified origin
Short-term O ₃ increase	$2.13 \cdot 10^{-13}$	0.267	$7.978 \cdot 10^{-13}$	
Long-term O ₃ decrease	-	-	-	
CH ₄ decrease	$1.77 \cdot 10^{-13}$	14.2	$1.451 \cdot 10^{-14}$	
Aerosols : Fuglestedt et al (2010)	$W m^{-2} kg^{-1}$			
Black carbon BC	$1.96 \cdot 10^{-9} (W m^{-2} kg_C^{-1})$	0.020		Not existent as Air emission

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Organic carbon OC	$-2.90 \cdot 10^{-10}$ ($W m^{-2} kg_c^{-1}$)	0.021		Not existent as Air emission
SO ₂	$-3.2 \cdot 10^{-10}$ ($W m^{-2} kg_{SO_2}^{-1} y$)	0.011		Sulfur dioxide Sulfate
Hydrogen (Hauglustaine et al 2022)	$1.30 \cdot 10^{-4}$ ($W m^{-2} ppbv^{-1}$)	2.5	$3.66 \cdot 10^{-13}$	Hydrogen
Aviation Air/lower stratosphere + upper troposphere	ERF sensitivity to emissions ($W m^{-2}$ $kg_emission^{-1} y$) Lee et al. (2021)*	Lifetime (years) Fuglestedt et al (2010)	Specific forcing ($W m^{-2} kg^{-1}$) used in this work	
NO _x :	$W m^{-2} kg_N^{-1} y$		$W m^{-2} kg_N^{-1}$	Nitrogen oxides
Short-term O ₃ increase	$3.44 \cdot 10^{-11}$	0.267	$1.288 \cdot 10^{-10}$	
Long-term O ₃ decrease	$-9.30 \cdot 10^{-12}$	12.02	$-7.737 \cdot 10^{-13}$	
CH ₄ decrease	$-1.87 \cdot 10^{-11}$	12.02	$-1.556 \cdot 10^{-12}$	
Stratospheric water vapor decrease	$-2.80 \cdot 10^{-12}$	12.02	$-2.329 \cdot 10^{-13}$	
Aerosols :				
SO ₂	$-1.99 \cdot 10^{-11}$ ($W m^{-2} kg_{SO_2}^{-1} y$)	0.011	$-1.810 \cdot 10^{-9}$ ($W m^{-2}$ $kg_{SO_2}^{-1}$)	Sulfur dioxide Sulfate
Soot (or BC)**	$1.007 \cdot 10^{-10}$ ($W m^{-2} kg_c^{-1} y$)	0.02	$5.035 \cdot 10^{-9}$ ($W m^{-2}$ kg_{BC}^{-1})	Not existent
Stratospheric water vapor increase	$5.20 \cdot 10^{-15}$ ($W m^{-2} kg_{H_2O}^{-1} y$)	0.08 (Lifetime at 12km, north hemisphere)	$6.50 \cdot 10^{-14}$ ($W m^{-2}$ $kg_{H_2O}^{-1}$)	Water
Contrail cirrus***	$9.36 \cdot 10^{-13}$ ($W m^{-2} km^{-1} y$)	0.00057	$1.64 \cdot 10^{-9}$ ($W m^{-2}$ km^{-1})	
Emission from shipping Air/low Air/unspecified Air/....	Radiative forcing	Lifetime (years)	Specific forcing ($W m^{-2} kg^{-1}$) used in this work	
Aerosols SO ₂ : Fuglestedt et al (2010)	$W m^{-2} kg_{SO_2}^{-1}$			

SO ₂ direct effect	-3.43 10 ⁻¹⁰	0011		
SO ₂ indirect effect	-3.54 10 ⁻⁹ (citing Lauer et al 2007, inventory A)	0.011		
NO _x :	W m ⁻² kg _N ⁻¹ y Fuglestedt et al (2010) citing Fuglestedt et al (2008)		W m ⁻² kg _N ⁻¹	
Short-term O ₃ increase	7.19 10 ⁻¹²	0.267	2.692 10 ⁻¹¹	
Long-term O ₃ decrease	-1.88 10 ⁻¹²	10.2	-1.843 10 ⁻¹³	
CH ₄ decrease	-7.56 10 ⁻¹²	10.2	-7.412 10 ⁻¹³	

*AR6 ch 6. indicates Lee et al 2021 as the best estimate of ERF from aviation

**Soot = BC and OC (Lee et al, 2021)

***Contrail cirrus : the value in Lee 2021, is in mW/m²/km. This unit is not correct, it should be mW/m²/(km/y). Demonstration from the GWP 100, 50, 20 values , using CO2 AGTPs (8.89526E-14; 5.1477E-14; 2.42365E-14). From the GWPs given by Lee, the iRFs (A/tau values) are in average 9.50096E-13. At 20 y, there is no more RF (contrails disappear), so iRF20=iRF50=iRF100. The specific ERF is thus 9.50096E-13/tau (0.00057 y).

Table 8. Updated values for the specific effective radiative forcing taken from IPCC AR6 ch 7. Chemical effects of CH₄ and N₂O are included in the radiative efficiency.

Species	Lifetime (Years)	Radiative Efficiency (W m ⁻² ppb ⁻¹)	GWP-20	GWP-100	GWP-500	GTP-50	GTP-100
CO ₂	Multiple	1.33 ± 0.16 × 10 ⁻⁵	1.	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
CH ₄ -fossil	11.8 ± 1.8	5.7 ± 1.4 × 10 ⁻⁴	82.5 ± 25.8	29.8 ± 11	10.0 ± 3.8	13.2 ± 6.1	7.5 ± 2.9
CH ₄ -non fossil	11.8 ± 1.8	5.7 ± 1.4 × 10 ⁻⁴	79.7 ± 25.8	27.0 ± 11	7.2 ± 3.8	10.4 ± 6.1	4.7 ± 2.9
N ₂ O	109 ± 10	2.8 ± 1.1 × 10 ⁻³	273 ± 118	273 ± 130	130 ± 64	290 ± 140	233 ± 110
HFC-32	5.4 ± 1.1	1.1 ± 0.2 × 10 ⁻¹	2693 ± 842	771 ± 292	220 ± 87	181 ± 83	142 ± 51
HFC-134a	14.0 ± 2.8	1.67 ± 0.32 × 10 ⁻¹	4144 ± 1160	1526 ± 577	436 ± 173	733 ± 410	306 ± 119
CFC-11	52.0 ± 10.4	2.91 ± 0.65 × 10 ⁻¹	8321 ± 2419	6226 ± 2297	2093 ± 865	6351 ± 2342	3536 ± 1511
PFC-14	50,000	9.89 ± 0.19 × 10 ⁻²	5301 ± 1395	7380 ± 2430	10,587 ± 3692	7660 ± 2464	9055 ± 3128

3.5 An example of application

An example of application is presented here to illustrate how the method can respond the question: *Does the studied system respect the European requirements to reduce impacts from 2030 and to be climate-neutral in 2050 (European Commission, 2025)?*

Additionally, it serves to respond the question: How to interpret the dynamic climate change results?

This example concerns a water treatment plant (WTP) for drinking water production by seawater desalting through a reverse osmosis process. This technology, albeit its high performance and treatment potential, has

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the disadvantage of high electricity consumption. The afforestation is considered here as the solution for the mitigation of GHG emissions from WTP system and for achieving its climate neutrality. Details on the elaboration of this example are given elsewhere (Tiruta-Barna, 2021).

Conventional LCA. The LCA product system encompasses the WTP lifecycle (plant construction, functioning and dismantling) and the forest planting and management as natural ecosystem. The functional unit is the production of 1m³ drinking water during 30 years, and starting in year 2020. Data sets already provided with ecoinvent 3.7 were used for WTP and forest. The “amount” of forest to be planted was calculated on the base of kg CO₂ -eq. LCA results in order to offset the WTP impact, i.e. to achieve neutrality as zero kg CO₂ -eq. (GWP100). Hence, for the functional unit: WTP counts for 2.33 kg CO₂ -eq. and the forest system for -2.33 kg CO₂-eq. from which -2.341 kg CO₂ -eq. corresponds to CO₂ captured and stored in biomass (a new forest) and +0.0081 kg CO₂-eq. corresponds to GHG emissions from forest management.

Dynamic LCA with dynamic climate change impact. In conventional LCA, the tree species doesn't play an important role (except for small differences in management operations). However, two species are considered here, Fagus and Pinus, with 140 and 50 years rotation period respectively. In this example, the temporalized inventory includes the WTP construction and forest planting during the first year (in 2020), WTP functioning over 30 years followed by infrastructure's end-of-life (landfill).

The results are presented in Figure 4. The spider diagram shows that WTP+Pinus afforestation is more performant than WTP+Fagus. Moreover, as shown in the top-left side chart, effective climate neutrality (defined as zero temperature increase, GMTC=0) could be achieved only after the neutrality goal by 2050 (t_{goalN}), i.e. 12 and 59 years after WTP dismantling (year 2062 and year 2109), with Pinus and Fagus respectively. Despite the long term (theoretically infinity) convergence of the two systems towards zero GMTC, for the time scale of this century, undesired behavior is observed especially for WTP+Fagus system. The temporality of CO₂ capture by Pinus is more adequate than the temporality of GHG emissions by WTP.

Figure 4. Results of the dynamic climate change impact method applied to the case study (for the significance of parameters see the section below).

3.6 A guide for interpreting the results

In the followings we propose a guide for how to interpret the results from the dynamic climate change approach. To be consistent with the Paris Agreement, three elements must be monitored (Rogelj et al., 2019): (1) the time at which Global Mean Surface Temperature (GMST) reaches its peak; (2) the level of warming at this time point; and (3) GMST evolution after its peak, either stable or decreasing. The impact indicators must be functions of time and adaptive with respect to the climate targets, and to respond to the need of adaptive mitigation.

The proposed climate impact indicators are based on the radiative forcing and on the global mean temperature change, and their integrated forms over the desired time horizons. The temperature is preferred to RF because: (i) the temperature is the measured physical parameter, and (ii) *the Paris Agreement focuses on temperature goals and its desired temporality*. However, care must be taken when using integrated metrics, because they give equal importance to climate impacts that occur at different points in time (the information about the peaks is lost).

The following aspects and rules could be considered when interpreting the results of dynamic LCA with dynamic climate change impact evaluation, adapted from Tiruta-Barna (2021). The indicators are presented in Table 9. For all indicators, “smaller is better” is the ranking rule between the compared systems.

- three reference time points are proposed: (1) the time of temperature peak followed by temperature decline or stabilization in the short term (prior to 2050), t_{goalST} ; (2) the time when climate neutrality should be accomplished, t_{goalN} , for example, $t_{\text{goalN}} = 2050$; and (3) a time for an additional long-term target, t_{LT} , i.e. $t_{\text{LT}} = 2100$.
- The indicators need to discriminate between systems having the same global net emissions (commonly expressed in kg CO₂-eq.) but with different temporalities and consequently different climate effects (to avoid, for example, postponing GHG emissions beyond 2050, or accelerating the current warming).
- The indicators need to correctly evaluate climate neutrality. Concerning the temporality, the selected points in time need to be able to describe the temperature evolution in a manner consistent with the Paris Agreement goals and be easily updatable following adjustments of these goals (e.g., achieving neutrality by $t_{\text{goalN}} = 2050$ or by $t_{\text{goalN}} = 2070$, etc.).
- The temperature peak is directly responsible for climate perturbation phenomena (IPCC, 2013), with larger climate impacts for higher peak amplitudes.
- Climate neutrality, in its physical interpretation (Fuglestedt et al., 2018), signifies that RF stabilizes in time; thus, there is no additional global temperature increase, i.e., GMTC is zero (or preferably negative) from this point in time ($t_{\text{neutrality}}$) forward. Obviously, early neutrality is preferred.
- Concerning $t_{\text{last_peak}}$, an early peak temperature followed by a decrease is preferred to a later peak because, as the peak approaches the time target, the probability of exceeding the temperature goal increases and it becomes increasingly difficult to deploy efficient carbon capture and storage (CCS) techniques to keep GMST below 1.5°C (or 2°C).
- In case of systems with multiple temperature peaks and/or neutrality points (GMTC=0), the last event is considered as time indicator (the time of the last peak, the time of the last neutral point) in order to not conceal temperature rebounds on the time course. GMTC_{max} corresponds to the highest peak.
- Finally, iGMTC is a measure of the accumulated heat that causes impacts such as ice melting and sea level rise; a smaller iGMTC results in a smaller impact.

Table 9. Proposed indicators for a multicriteria evaluation of climate change impact in dynamic LCA.

Category of impact & Parameter	Indicator	Notation
<u>Radiative forcing</u>		
“emission metrics”	Radiative forcing at a given moment	RF
	Integrated radiative forcing	iRF
<u>Temperature</u>		
Global mean temperature change (GMTC)	Temperature maximum peak registered	GMTC_{max}
	<i>Paris Agreement - Climate neutrality</i>	
	Time of climate neutrality achievement when GMTC=0	$t_{\text{GMTC}=0}$
	-Deviation from the goal	$t_{\text{neutrality}} = t_{\text{GMTC}=0} - t_{\text{goalN}}$
	<i>If climate neutrality not achieved</i>	
Time of the last temperature peak or the beginning of temperature decrease or stabilization	$t_{\text{T starts decrease}}$	
-Deviation from the goal	$t_{\text{last_peak}} = t_{\text{T starts decrease}} - t_{\text{goalST}}$	
<u>Heat</u>		
Accumulated heat (iGMTC)	Integrated temperature change at long term, taken here as 2100	iGMTC_{LT} for $t_{\text{LT}} = 2100$

3.7 References

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4 CONCLUSION

Through this deliverable, we advanced and harmonized the assessment of dynamic carbon footprint, with a focus on forestry systems. The relevance for such biobased systems is striking due to the uptake of CO₂ and temporary storage before release at the end of life. We improved both the inventory (objectives 1-2) and impact assessment (objectives 3-4).

For our first objective, LIST managed to update the temporal database of DyPLCA to entail temporal data for all ecoinvent 3.11 processes (~27000), working further on the limited update to ecoinvent 3.10 done in a previous project (CALIMERO). Such a temporal database, in combination with the DyPLCA tool (a dedicated tool for dynamic LCA), allows for a fully dynamic carbon footprint where temporal distribution for all flows (here climate change stressors) of all processes of a life cycle are considered. This is still unmatched in literature by any other approach. Bear in mind that this raw database is confidential.

Regarding the second objective, AAU & LIST collaborated to derive temporal CO₂ profiles for forestry systems as present in ecoinvent 3.11. AAU, ran their dedicated carbon flux model for representative/matched datasets for ecoinvent forestry processes. Yet, readily, only for about 60% of the ecoinvent forestry processes, AAU found representative datasets. Nevertheless, we cover the conventional European species. LIST, then derived functions based on the yearly obtained CO₂ fluxes. These were converted into compatible programming code and implemented in the DyPLCA database. Note that no flow amounts were altered from ecoinvent, but just a temporal distribution added or superimposed.

To address the third objective, the calculation behind the Climate Change Impact tool (CCI-tool) of INSA were revisited and updated based on latest insights, namely from the IPCC reports. Concretely, INSA included the indirect effects and the carbon cycle feedback in the characterization.

Finally, INSA derived and included the computation for short lived climate forcers, e.g. NO_x, based on literature data. This model uses the specific effective radiative forcing (if available; if not, the specific radiative forcing), and the perturbation time (or lifetime).

To illustrate the dynamic climate change impact factors, the implication of a dynamic carbon footprint versus a conventional one was also illustrated by INSA through a case on water treatment with afforestation of two different species for counterbalancing greenhouse gas emissions of the water treatment plant. At the end, a way of interpreting a harmonized set of dynamic climate change impact metrics is presented.

Further research opportunities are of course still present and can be explored. Runs of the DyPLCA model with its database, are ongoing and will be presented as part of the deliverable of task 6.2. A second one is prospective characterization of the climate change impact of future climate forcer emissions, considering different future conditions. For this deliverable, data, information and modelling results in literature, were too limited, but further endeavors are conducted in light of task 3.3 of LCA4BIO. A third one, concerns land use change effects, but this will be covered in Work Package 4 of LCA4BIO.